

АСОС ВА ХОСИЛА СЕМАЛАРИ БИЛАН БИРГА ЎЗЛАШГАН СЎЗЛАР

Нарзиев Наврўз Толлибоевич

Самарқанд давлат чет тиллар институти,

+998994461067. mega_n1986@mail.ru

Аннотация: Яхлит бир бутун сема ва синтактик хусусиятлари билан ёки маълум бир маъноси ва функцияни бажаришига кўра сўзлар асос тилдан бошқа бир тилга ўзлаштирилиши мумкин. Ушбу мақолада хорижий тиллардан асос ва хосила семаларига кўра ўзбек тилига ўзлашган бир неча сўзлар таҳлил қилинган.

Калит сўзлар: сема, изоҳли луғат, эълон, шиллинг

Аннотация: Слова могут быть ассимилированы из базового языка в другой язык с целым семафором и синтаксическими особенностями или в соответствии с выполнением определенного значения и функции. В статье анализируются несколько слов с иностранных языков на узбекский по основной и производной семантике.

Ключевые слова: сема, толковый словарь, афиша, шиллинг.

Abstract: Words can be assimilated from the base language to another language with a whole semaphore and syntactic features or according to the performance of a certain meaning and function. This article analyzes several words from foreign languages into Uzbek according to the basic and derivative semantics.

Key words: sema, Glossary, poster(afficher), shilling.

Афиша. “Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли лугати”да: Спектакль, концерт, лекция ва шу кабилар ҳақида кўринарли жойларга ёпиштириладиган эълон.

Afficher. n.f. Feuille imprimee, souvent illustree, portant un avis officiel, publicitaire, etc., placardee dans un lieu public, etre annonce par des affiches, en parlant d'un spectacle. **Afficher.v.t.** 1)Placarder, appose (une affiche).2)Annoncer par voie d'affiche. 3)Montrer avec ostentation, etaler. **Afficher. n.f.** Petite affiche.

Трамвай. “Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли лугати” да:

Электр кучи билан ишлайдиган шаҳар ер усти темир йўли. Шундай йўлнинг поезда, вагонлари. Инглиз тилида: **Tram (also tramcar)** US Streetcar, trolley, noun a vehicle that carries passengers and is usual driven by electricity. Trams run on rails laid along the streets of a town.

Транзистор. “Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли лугати” да:

Электр сигналларни кўпайтирувчи ярим ўтказгичли электрон асбоб

Транзисторли приёмник.

Инглиз тилида: **Transistor.** A small electronic device used in radios, televisions and similar appliances, for controlling an electrical signal as it passas along a circuit. (Also Tran, sistor radio) a radio with transistors, esp a small one that can be carried.

Шиллинг. “Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли лугати” да:

Англияда 1/20 фунт стерлингга тенг танга пул.

Австрияда ва бази бир африка мамлакатларида пул бирлиги.

Инглиз тилида: Shilling. noun.

(Until 1971) a British coin worth 12 old pennies; one 20th of a pound.

The basic unit of money in Keniya, Uganda and Tanzania.

Стандард. Маҳсулотларнинг сифати, таркиби жиҳатдан бир хил бўлишини таъминлайдиган намуна. *Давлат стандарти.*

Инглиз тилида: STANDARD, n. 1.(often Plural) a level of quality; a school which sets high standards of behavior. We provide a first-class standard of service. Mountain /raise/ improve safety standards. 2.[C.U] a specified level of quality: His work does not reach the required standard. I am afraid your work is not up to standard Local beaches fall short of/do not meet European standards of cleanliness. Standard lamp (us floor lamp) n, a tall lamp which has its base on the floor, used esp. in a living room (LIVING) Standard of living n (plural Standards of living) a level of comfort and wealth amiable to a person or group in a particular country, area, etc.: They have / enjoy a high standard of living.

Старт. (инглизча) 1. Спорт мусобақаларининг бошланиш ўрни. Учиш аппаратининг ердан кўтарилиш жойи. *Старт чизиг`и старт майдон.* **2.** Спорт мусобақаларининг бошланиш пайти. Учиш аппаратининг ердан кўтарилиш пайти. “Биз янги космик старт бўсағасида турибмиз.”

Инглиз тилида: START (2) [sta:t] V –note at begin. **1.** ~ (out) to begin a journey;

to leave: We plan to start (out) at 6 o'clock. *I started after her* (i.e. followed her) *to tell her the news*. **2.** To begin sth./To do sth: to begin to happen; I start work at 9 am, I had to start (i.e., begin using) a new tin of paint. *He's just started a new job. I arrived after the play had started I have had enough criticism for one day- don't you start. They started (the concert) with a piece by MOZART*. **3.** – **(on) sth (a)** to begin doing a job an activity, a piece of work, etc.; start **(on)** one's journey home. Have you started **(on)** (i.e., begun to write or read) your next book yet? It's time to get started on / time we got started on (i.e., began) the washing up. **(b)~ sb on (doing) sth to make sb begin doing sth:** start babies on solid food. **4. (A)** (of a machine, etc.) to begin operating; The car won't start. **(b)** To make a machine etc. begin operating: I can't start the car. **5.** To bring sth into existence; to cause or enable sb/sth to begin or begin happening: start fire. He decided to start a newspaper. His uncle started him in business. (i.e., helped him, eg. by giving money). The news started me thinking. The smoke started her coughing.

Чампион. Спорт мусобақаларида, ўйинларда ғолиб чиққан, биринчи ўринни егаллаган кишига бериладиган унвон ва шу унвонга ега бўлган киши. “Бокс бўйича мамлакат чемпиони”.

Инглиз тилада: CHAMPION (also infml. champ.). 1. A person, a team, an animal, etc. that has one a competition; a chess champion. *The English football teams were world champions in 1996*. The heavy weight (boxing) champion of the world, a champion swimmer/ horse/marrow. 2. A person who fights, argues or speaks in support of sb/sth; a champion of the poor/ of woman's rights. Champion v. to support sb/sth to defend sb/sth vigorously: [Vn] champion the cause of gay rights. Championship n, (often plural) 1. A contest to decide who the champion is: win the world championship. The European Championships are being held in Rome, a championship medal. 2. [C] The position of being a champion: The Championship is ours—note at SPORT. [U]strong and active support: her lifelong championship of good causes.

Фойдаланилган адабиётлар:

1. Раҳимов А. Лексик ва семантик деривация муаммолари. –Т., 2011.

2. Н.Г. Комлез “Словарь новых иностранных слов” МГУ., 2012 г.
3. О. Жуманиёзов Инглиз тилидан ўзбек тилига ўзлашган сўзлар, монография, 1987 й.
4. Н.Т. Нарзиев,- Сўз ясовчи бирликларнинг семантик муносабати., “Чет тилларни ўрганишнинг турлича ёндашувлари: муаммо ва ечимлар” халқаро илмий-амалий конференцияматериаллари, Жиззах 2021й.
5. Н. Т.Нарзиев - Инглиз тилида лексик деривация ҳодисасининг воқеланиши “Чет тилларни ўрганишнинг турлича ёндашувлари: муаммо ва ечимлар” халқаро илмий-амалий конференцияматериаллари, Жиззах 2021й.
6. Н.Т.Нарзиев Lexical meaning of the word, conferences.kz Инновационное развитие науки и образования С.278-280. 2020.